

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Ntrakwah****FIRST NAME: Kwadwo****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (MSWord version 16.0 on MacBook)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is plagiarism?

- When the writer uses a source of information without crediting the author of that source of information.¹**
- When the writer only quotes another author's exact words and gives him credit.
- When the writer uses primary sources.
- When the writer describes something in his own words.

2. Which of these is the attitude of writers to feedback?

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Gulma Kabiru, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

- Feedback is unnecessary as only the writer has undertaken the research and knows why he has written those thoughts.
 - Experienced writers know that nothing is more valuable than comments from a trusted reader.²**
 - Feedback can delay the progress being made by the writer.
 - It is very difficult to get good feedback.
3. When most of your evidence is quantitative, or you must communicate a large set of data, it is best to?
- Use different types of data.
 - Avoid using data altogether.
 - Present data graphically.³**
 - Change how you collect the data.
4. Citation management tools are an excellent resource, and so you should
- Rely on them one hundred percent.
 - Not use them at all.
 - Double-check your data and double-check your citations, as these tools do make errors.⁴**
 - Use them as you please.

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Ninth Edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 127.

³ Ibid., 87.

⁴ Ibid., 146.

5. The proposed title for a dissertation should.
- Be simple and straightforward.
 - Should be very interesting for the reader.
 - Broadly describe the topic.
 - Include participants and a proper setting for the research.**⁵
6. The table of contents for the dissertation should always include.
- A dedication page.
 - An acknowledgments page.
 - All of the components of the dissertation, including all five levels of APA headings.**⁶
 - Anything else that the writer wants included.
7. Which of the following is the correct definition of the statement of the problem?
- What goes into the abstract of the dissertation.
 - A succinct statement of the dilemma that the research questions are intended to resolve.**⁷
 - The research questions that the writer will be asking.
 - The key features of the title of the dissertation.

⁵ James P Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition (Tallahassee :Florida State University, 2017), 24.

⁶ *ibid.*, 25.

⁷ *Ibid.*, 28.

8. Which of the following should not be in the Abstract of the dissertation?
- The statement of the problem.
 - Research question and corresponding hypothesis.
 - Measures operationalizing the variables Apply.
 - The Bibliography.**⁸
9. Which style guide does EUCLID recommend for students to use?
- European Commission Rule of Style.
 - WHO Rule of Style.
 - Turabian and Chicago Rule of Style (Turabian).**⁹
 - Oxford Rule of Style.
10. What is applied research?
- When research addresses a conceptual problem that does not have a direct practical consequence.
 - When research only improves the understanding of a community of researches.
 - When research addresses a conceptual problem, that does have practical consequences.**¹⁰
 - When research has donor funding.

⁸ Ibid., 26.

⁹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Gulma Kabiru, 41.

¹⁰ Kate L. Turabian, 29.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021

Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.